

THE BOUNDARIES BETWEEN HEARING AND EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE

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ABSTRACT

This article examines music therapy as an interdisciplinary field that explores the relationship between auditory perception and human emotional processes. From a scientific and theoretical perspective, the impact of music therapy on an individual's psychological and physical health is analyzed. The origins and development of music therapy as an independent method of psychological and pedagogical intervention are discussed. Particular attention is given to the effectiveness of music therapy in reducing stress levels and stabilizing emotional states.

Keywords: music therapy, emotions, mental health, W. A. Mozart.

Music is one of the oldest and most universal forms of expression of humanity, transcending cultural, linguistic and temporal boundaries. It is not only an artistic form, but also a complex phenomenon closely related to cognitive, emotional and physiological processes. Music can be an effective tool in supporting psychological and physical health by evoking deep feelings in a person, recalling memories and influencing mood and behavior. Music is considered a central object of scientific research in the study of the human mind and psyche. In recent decades, the therapeutic potential of music has been increasingly recognized, and this field - music therapy - has a solid scientific basis and is widely used. Music therapy has been formed as a special practice aimed at regulating a person's emotional state, reducing stress, stabilizing mood, as well as supporting cognitive and physical health. The term "music therapy" comes from the Greek-Latin language and means "treatment with music". There are many definitions of the concept of "music therapy". The majority of scientists consider music therapy to be an auxiliary tool of psychotherapy, a means of special preparation of patients for the use of complex therapeutic methods. One of the first people to confirm the significant influence of music on the mental and physical state of a person was the Greek scientist and philosopher Pythagoras. As can be seen from Iamblichus' work "The Life of Pythagoras", "if someone listens to beautiful rhythms and songs, then such a person receives musical education, using melodies and rhythms, human morality and passions are treated, and the initial harmony of mental forces is established".

The creation and history of music therapy: Music therapy is closely connected with the history of mankind, its roots go back to ancient times. In ancient Greece and Egypt, doctors and philosophers used music to treat mental and physical illnesses. For example, Plato and Aristotle noted that music can have a powerful influence on the human psyche and shape socio-cultural behavior. In the Middle Ages, religious ceremonies and contemplative music were widely used in Europe and Asia for spiritual education and treatment. During this period, music was considered more of a religious and spiritual educational tool, but its therapeutic potential gradually gained scientific attention. The modern concept of music therapy began to take shape in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. During this period, psychiatrists and educators began to scientifically study the effects of music on the human psyche and social adaptation. In the 1940s and 1950s, music therapists began to be trained through accredited programs in the United States, and in the 1950s, the American Music Therapy Association (AMTA) was founded, which ensured that music therapy became a formal and scientific field.

The relationship between auditory and emotional processes in music therapy: Music works mainly through two main processes in influencing a person's mental and physical state: auditory and emotional experience. The auditory process is associated with the reception of a musical signal by the nervous system and its interpretation by the brain. This process allows a person to concentrate,

perceive rhythm and tonality, as well as activate memory and cognitive functions. The emotional process is expressed in the emotional reactions that the heard musical signal evokes in the human psyche. Studies show that the timbre, rhythm, melody and speed of music significantly change a person's mood, emotional state and stress level. For example, slow and soothing music normalizes heart rate and blood pressure, while rhythmic and fast music leads to an increase in activity and energy. In music therapy, these two processes complement each other. Through hearing, the technical properties of music are perceived, and the emotional process transforms this signal into a personal emotional experience. Thus, music becomes a means of regulating a person's mental state and ensuring emotional balance. Modern neuropsychological studies also show that sensitivity to music and emotional responses are associated with the activity of brain centers - the limbic system and the prefrontal cortex, which explains the effectiveness of music therapy on a neurophysiological basis. Auditory and emotional processes combine as two main factors in the therapeutic effect of music, which is the main mechanism for regulating a person's psychoemotional state and reducing stress.

The role of music therapy in reducing stress: Music therapy is an effective tool for reducing stress and ensuring psychoemotional stability. Studies show that listening to music or its active use affects the human nervous system, reduces cortisol levels and reduces excessive activity of the sympathetic nervous system. At the same time, music normalizes heart rate and blood pressure. Forms of music therapy: There are 3 main forms of music therapy: receptive, active, integral. Receptive music therapy (passive) is characterized by the fact that the patient does not actively participate in the process of music therapy sessions, taking the position of a simple listener. He is offered to listen to various musical compositions or to listen to different sounds that are appropriate for his mental health and stage of treatment. Active methods of music therapy are based on active work with musical materials: instrumental playing, singing.

Examples of the effects of music therapy: According to several scientific studies, listening to Mozart's D major sonata helps reduce the number of epileptic seizures in patients (the so-called Mozart effect). However, the reliability of the results of this study was hampered by its limitations and the inability to repeat the results in subsequent studies. Doctors recommend that music helps relax muscles, especially during fast walking and running, and can be used as an additional rehabilitation therapy to maintain good physical condition in obese people. In addition, music has a stimulating effect on mood and emotions, which allows you to maintain a sports spirit and thus has a long-term effect on fitness achievements. Properly selected melodies, musical compositions, improvisations are a convenient tool for working with memory and the unconscious. Music improves thinking and memory processes. Sounds interact with associative structures, pulling real memories and experiences to the surface and into consciousness.

In conclusion, it can be said that music therapy is an effective and scientifically based tool for supporting human mental and physical health. Research shows that music regulates the psychoemotional state, reduces stress levels, and provides mental stability through the auditory process and sensory experience of a person.

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